

INSPECTION OF ACCIDENTS AND EMPLOYEE
HEALTH AT "UZBEKISTAN RAILWAYS" JSC
ENTERPRISES

Talipov Murodjon Takhirovich,

deputy of the Department of Strategic Development,
Organization of Industrial Activities and Labor Protection of
JSC "Uzbekiston Temir Yollari"

Abstract: This article describes the observed accidents in enterprises, organizations and institutions belonging to "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC from 2018 to 2021. It is about the state of the health process of employees working in production enterprises.

Key words: accident, serious injury, minor injury, fatality, etc.

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Investigations involving on the job injuries require significant attention to detail. Investigations into health & safety incidents seek to identify the causes of work related injuries, helping employers take appropriate action to prevent future injuries. Proper evidence collection and the information gathered during investigation interviews contribute to the success of workplace incident investigations.

Why Look Into Incidents Regarding Health and Safety?

The Uzbekistan Railways JSC Centre for Occupational Health and Safety states that the following are "reasons to investigate a workplace accident":

to identify the cause of accidents and take precautions against reoccurring incidents, to satisfy any legal obligations, to figure out how much an accident will cost, to ascertain whether the relevant safety requirements are being followed, to handle claims for workers' compensation.

Here are five things to think about when looking into workplace incidents.

1. Address Direct Risk – Treat the wound right away. Make sure the right care is given if the wounded worker needs hospitalisation, medical attention, or even simple first aid. Ensure that incident reports are completed accurately and that any medical interventions are adequately documented. Recording the location of the workplace accident is also crucial. Until this area has been examined and found to be safe to reenter, keep it off.

Closing off the location makes it easier to preserve the evidence so that investigators may gather and examine it. Make a list of the names of any witnesses who were there when the incident occurred. Interviewing witnesses is a crucial aspect of the investigation since it offers valuable insights into the occurrence. If the incident needs to be reported to an occupational health and safety board or organization, make sure the claim is filed as soon as possible.

2. Gathering of Evidence – “Work environment, job constraints, and supervisory or worker experience can all play a part in workplace injuries,” according to the Construction Safety Association of Ontario. To ascertain how each contributed to the disaster, these factors need to be investigated”. Take photos and record observations before removing anything from the scene of the occurrence. When gathering tangible proof, mark the evidence's location and date of collection on the label.

The i-Sight (now Case IQ) Investigation Software is one example of a case management system that assists investigators in gathering, organising, and monitoring evidence from health and safety accidents. The evidence is assigned exhibit numbers and bar codes by i-Sight (now Case IQ), enabling each investigator to access the evidence along with a synopsis.

The following is a list of things to think about when gathering evidence for an inquiry. These inquiries aid in determining the course of events preceding the mishap.

The following list combines recommendations from the Chemical Plant Safety Resources Blog post titled "Industrial Accident Investigation Procedures" with those found on the CUPE website:

Places and positions of the injured worker or workers, Safety devices in use, equipment, chemicals, or other materials used at the scene of the injury, Was the worker donning the required goggles, helmets, and boots?, Equipment damage: state of safety protections, controls, and devices, Existence of malfunctioning or missing components, The workspace's cleanliness, weather circumstances (did the accident happen outside), Lighting conditions: dimly lighted areas with narrow visibility, Noise levels, Training provided to the employee prior to operating or working in the area, Time of day, Were company procedures being followed?,

3. Interviews for Inquiry – Conduct interviews with the injured worker, managers, and any witnesses who were there when the incident occurred. When allowed, record the interviews on video, audio, or in writing. After the interviews are over, investigators can review the information using these accounts. By speaking with the injured worker, investigators can get a first-hand description of the incident.

However, witnesses could be a more reliable source of information depending on the severity of the injuries. For instance, the victim's description of the events may be incomplete or skewed because of their condition if the injury caused them to lose consciousness or go into shock.

Conducting interviews with supervisors is crucial since they can furnish details about the training the staff member has had, the dates of any new enhancements, or evaluations of the equipment and safety protocols implemented at work.

An abundance of information about the occurrence is available through witness interviews. Interview only those who are knowledgeable about the accident in any way. Advise interviewees not to discuss the circumstances or the interview with others. Inform witnesses of the reason for the interview while conducting one.

The purpose of the interviews is to obtain more data so that preventive action can be taken. Interviews are not conducted in order to assign blame or make accusations. Find out what happened right after the disaster and what happened before it happened.

4. Findings Report – Companies may be compelled by law in some places to disclose the results of their investigations and the steps they took to address any issues that were found. Gather interview replies and case evidence for in-depth examination.

Investigators can generate reports using i-Sight (now Case IQ) with just one click. Data that has been entered into the case file is extracted and prepared for distribution in a report template. After the data has been examined, draft potential fixes for the issue.

5. Remedial Measures – Make the necessary adjustments right now. After the reason or causes of the accident have been identified, address the issues and stop similar accidents involving health and safety in the future. Record the process of making corrections. Describe the actions done and the people who oversaw them. Documents detailing corrective actions offer proof for the adjustments made during the investigation. Legally, these acts must be documented in certain states or nations.

The following are a few instances of corrective actions:

machinery replacement or maintenance, putting up signs to encourage people to use safety gear, issue warnings, and take other required steps, Instruction, Establishing or strengthening safety protocols.

Figure 1. Accidents that occurred in enterprises, organizations and institutions of "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC from 2018 to 2021.

Accidents that the victim or witnesses failed to report to the employer during business hours, or that the victim or someone defending his interests requested that they be allowed to continue working, as well as those that the (chief) state labour technical inspector for labour protection requested be investigated, will be reviewed within 30 days of the application being submitted or the instruction being received. After the application of the accident has been carefully reviewed, taking into consideration all circumstances, witness testimony, and other evidence, the question of creating an N-1 document is determined. To prevent accidents, Uzbekistan Railways JSC is implementing a number of initiatives.

Literature

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